
Urbanization Process Of The Tribal And The Need Prospects For Urban Development In The Sixth Scheduled Tribal Areas Of Tripura For Aligning In The Modern Livelihood Economy.

Peter Prasanta Debbarma

*Asst. Professor, Department of Geography
R.K Mahavidyalaya, Kailashahar, Unakoti, Tripura*

Abstract

The growth pole theory which is related to urban development is the main mechanism and themes in the subject of Regional Planning and Development. In the modern economy, the urban growth center plays an important driving force in developing any region and raising the economic status of the people by offering various and series of opportunities for the livelihood of the tribal society. In this context, the assessment of urban composition and urbanization rate of Scheduled tribes becomes the main crux of the study. The latest urban composition of the tribes of Tripura is hardly 2 % of the total population of Tripura. The extent of urbanization of the tribal societies and urban composition is extremely small as they are predominantly rural-based with their strong roots in forest economy and dependence on subsistence agriculture. The assessments on the urban composition of ST of Tripura are being compared and assessed at the level of North-East, State and Districts and in Cities and towns of Tripura to get their vivid picture in the map of urbanization.

This paper has also examined the role of the State and its administrative functions of Sixth scheduled areas, regarding their initiatives being taken and the drawbacks in urbanizing of the scheduled tribes of Tripura. The general observation of the shifting trend of the tribal and their nature of embracing urban culture are being identified out. The concept of town building and policies for increasing the urbanization rate of Scheduled tribes of Tripura are being strategically discussed and explained out for the betterment of the urban welfare of the tribes.

Keywords: *Scheduled Tribes, Urban, Growth Centre, Composition, Livelihood, Towns, Economy.*

1. INTRODUCTION: The topic titled “*Urbanization process of the Tribal and the need Prospects for urban development in the Sixth Schedule Tribal areas of Tripura for aligning in the modern livelihood economy*” is about the assessment of the urban composition of Scheduled tribes in the cities and towns of Tripura. The task of the researcher is in finding out the numbers of ST residing in towns and cities and to understand their settlement from rural to urban areas over time which may be referred to as Urbanization. The paper also highlighted the reasons behind the low urban share population of Scheduled Tribes. The paper examines the role of TTADDC in building towns in the sixth scheduled areas. The paper will then generalize the need for building towns in the sixth schedule areas for diversifying the economic activities of the Scheduled Tribes.

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The Extent of urbanization is known to be positively correlated with the degree of economic development and performance in literacy rate and in maintaining quality education level. As is well known all tribes of Tripura not only predominantly rural in residential characteristics, they mainly live in the inaccessible hilly hamlets, many of which are located in protected or even in the reserved forest areas. The assessment of the urban composition and urbanization of the scheduled will reflect the overall status developments of the

tribes. As urbanization is an important indicator in measuring the level of higher education and alignment in the present economy of livelihood. The study related to urbanization and urban composition of ST in the important cities and towns of Tripura; and the crucial need for urbanizing them, become the significant and modern approaches for developing any community or tribes.

3. REVIEW ON LITERATURE RELATED TO URBAN STUDY OF TRIPURA AND FINDING THE RESEARCH GAPS:

There are rare attempts of papers that have been carried out on the study of urbanization of the tribes of Tripura. The research paper which needs to be noted is by *Malabika Das Gupta (2014)* has done a project on '*Urbanization of the Tribes of Tripura* (displaying on 2001 census). Her study is however related to the socio-economic profile of the tribes concerning urbanization. The author had not discussed in terms geographical terms of urban exclusion and the role of the sixth scheduled areas in determining the size of the urban composition of the tribes.

There are other project surveys by the Ministry of Development of North-Eastern Region on '*Social Assessment and Tribal Developmental Framework-North-East Livelihood*'-Draft Final Report. May 2011. This highlights the data and as there are not many illustrations done on Tripura perspective as the topic was vast with the inclusion of North-East Region. Another paper that needs to be identified out is by Aashish Khakha, a Ph.D. research scholar at the School of Development Studies, Tata Institute of Social Sciences made a study on '*Tribes and Urbanisation in North East India-Issues and Challenges-Economic and Political weekly.*, Mumbai. This study is however on generalization study on an urban study on North-East tribes from a sociological perspective.

4. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEMS AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

The study of urbanization rate and urban composition of the Scheduled tribes of Tripura are showing exceedingly low trend and micro composition of an urban population of the State. In comparison, their counterpart predominant ST states of North-East States have shown increasing and positive trends with their sizeable significant population embracing urban culture and settlements. In this context scenario, there arise some important questions, verification, and in-depth searches for knowing the reasons and causes behind the micro-urban population of ST of Tripura. The need for assessing and evaluating the growth trend of urbanization of ST of Tripura under the purview of Census period decades at the State level, District level, and in cities and towns of Tripura becomes the pivot of the study. There are certain questions to be made to get the findings of the Study.

- (i). What are the determining factors for the reason behind the low urbanization rate and micro-urban composition of ST of Tripura?
- (ii). What is the perspective of Scheduled tribes of Tripura in embracing urban culture?
- (iii). What are the roles of the Sixth scheduled area administrative functions and the role of the State in urbanizing the ST of Tripura?
- (iv). What Strategies can be approached for the town building and increasing the urban composition of the tribes?

OBJECTIVES: The study is based on specific objectives and hence, it has only two objectives to be met out:

(i) To assess the urban composition and the urbanization rate of the Scheduled tribes of Tripura and their identification of exclusion from the urban pockets.

(ii) To suggest some measures in Town building strategies and development in the Sixth Scheduled areas to boost the economy of the Tribes for diversified occupations.

5. METHODOLOGY:

The methodologies involved in this paper are primarily based on the study of Census Records of India-Tripura State Report, North-east India -Rural and Urban composition of the scheduled tribes. The study of Urbanization rate and urban composition is being compared with other scheduled Tribes of North-East States. The Urban compositions of Scheduled Tribes are then exclusively discussed at the State level with its distribution across the districts of the State. The composition of ST in important cities and towns of Tripura are presented out to understand the distribution pattern of Urbanized Scheduled Tribes of Tripura.

The historical census records from 1961 to 2011 census depicting and selecting the urban composition of the Scheduled tribes of Tripura has been projected out for finding the growth trend and level of urbanization of the tribes. The exclusion of urban centers of Sixth Scheduled areas is represented through map figures for identifying the concentrated location and situations of Towns and cities in the General area. The data procured relating to urban composition are then projected through cartographic charts and diagrams, for better analyzing the urban exclusion of the tribes. The general observational and description and its present urban life of Scheduled tribes have also been assessed. The town building issues are studied with the concept of regional development and various strategies have been sought with the chief role of government in urbanizing the scheduled tribes of Tripura.

6. DATA SOURCES:

The data sources involved in this presentation of paper are purely based on Secondary source data-Census of India, RGI related to the Study Area, and Urban prospects of the Scheduled Tribes of Tripura. The Annual Report- Economic Report, Urban Report by Govt. of Tripura, Statistical Abstract, and Tripura at Glance, etc are being referred. The Tribal Welfare Department websites, TTAADC websites, Directorate of Employment and services. The data are procured from Urban Development-Cities and towns of Tripura. There are several Books and research and Journals related to urban status also being referred to.

7. DISCUSSION AND EVALUATION:

(a). Present Urban Status of the Scheduled Tribes of Tripura: The nature of the economic activities of ST of Tripura has not changed much even after many decades of Indian Independence. They are still predominantly engaged with rural forest economy and symbol bearers of subsistence traditional economy. How far Tribal can continue selling only forest products and subsistence agricultural products to the passerby along the roads? There need to be diversified occupations for aligning them in the stream of the Modern economy. The total population engulfing in the traditional rural economy will become an obsolete and inappropriate model of the economy, if there are no scopes of urban growth centers.

The sad and astonishing part of the Tribal of Tripura is they are forming staggering low in urban composition than the counterpart tribes of other predominant Tribal States of North-East. In the Sixth

Scheduled areas, there is hardly any urban growth center that has sprung up which can provide scopes for business and self-employment to the unemployed tribal. In recent decades, some of the Tribes are seen to be migrating to the Capital Agartala and in other important towns of the State. This type of rural to urban migration is not going to develop economically to the sixth Schedule areas; instead, the powers of purchasing classified Tribal groups have been transferred to the City. The price of the land is also unusually high and for which large sections of the tribal section cannot afford to buy a piece of land in the existing Cities and Towns of the State. The most appropriate strategy is building a model urban growth center in several Tribal dominated spots of Sixth Schedule areas to increase the urban composition of the tribes. Figure No.1 given depicts the presents the status of the urban and rural composition of ST in the State of Tripura.

To understand clearly, the urban picture of Scheduled Tribes of Tripura, the comparison study on ST urban population at the North-East level, State composition and its Districts variations along with the urban spots study in various towns and cities of Tripura reflects the position of ST in Urban map.

(b) A comparative study of ST Urban Population composition in North-East India: Most of the North-Eastern states are predominantly having ST populations except Assam, Tripura, and Sikkim. Among the North-East states, the ST urban dwellers of Tripura represent a low micro-composition of the urban population. The comparison between the total Urban Population of the State and the total ST urban composition of Tripura shows the lowest figure among the North-Eastern States. *Table No:1* shows the Urban ST population of the North-East States for understanding the position of ST of Tripura in terms of urban population at the North-East Level.

Table No.1: Urban composition of ST in North-East India, Census 2011

State	Total State Population	ST population	Total Urban population	Urban composition of ST
ARUNACHAL PRADESH	1383727	951821	317363	161975
ASSAM	31205576	3884371	43985542	218966
MANIPUR	2570390	902740	834154	111614

MEGHALAYA	2966889	2555861	595450	418970
MIZORAM	1097206	1036115	571771	528648
NAGALAND	1978502	1710973	570966	404135
SIKKIM	610577	206360	153578	39214
TRIPURA	3673917	1166813	961453	49247

Source: NER Data bank, Census of India, 2011

Table No.2 depicts that the ST of Tripura only forms 5.12 percent of the total 31 percent comprising of Scheduled Tribes.

Table No.2: Percentage rate of Urban Population

State	The population of ST %	Urban ST population%
ARUNACHAL PRADESH	68%	51%
ASSAM	12%	5.00%
MANIPUR	35.10%	13.40%
MEGHALAYA	70.40%	70.40%
MIZORAM	94.40%	92.50%
NAGALAND	86%	70.80%
SIKKIM	33.80%	25%
TRIPURA	31%	5.12%

It is understood that ST urban Population is exceedingly low when compared to other parts of North-East India. Tripura with 31 percent of the ST population is only accounting 5.10 percent of the ST population. It is also to be noted that Assam also accounts for 5.00 percent of the urban composition of ST. However, it is to be noted out that ST only forms 12 percent of the ST population and its Urban Population figure is 21,8966 whereas the ST population figure of Tripura is only 49,247 which is very low.

(c). **Growth trend of ST urban population of Tripura based on a census from 1961 to 2011:** The below Table no.3 presents the growth of ST population from 1961 to 2011 which are abstracted from Census of India-Tripura. The percentage composition of the ST population in the state just ranges from 3.59 to 5.10 with hardly a 2 % increase in five decades. The growth trend is a snail and stagnant with only minor variations since the last two decades.

Year	Total Population of the State	Urban population other than ST population	ST urban Population	Percentage of STs in the urban population of the State	Total Urban Population of the State	Total Level of Urbanization
1961	1142005	99299	3698	3.59	102997	9.02
1971	1556342	156875	5485	3.38	162360	10.43
1981	2053058	217900	7668	3.40	225568	10.99
1991	2757205	407640	14081	3.34	421721	15.30
2001	3199203	520321	25429	4.66	545750	17.06
2011	3673917	912206	49247	5.10	961453	26.17

Source: Census of India of Different Census years

Table No.4 highlights that the urban composition of the ST of Tripura is marginally low and the composition of others (non-ST) urban population occupies the lion share with constant 95 percent and above over the 5 decades.

Year	Urban population other than ST population	Percentage of other in the urban population of Tripura	ST urban Population	Percentage of STs in the urban population of the State
1961	99299	96.41	3698	3.59
1971	156875	96.62	5485	3.38
1981	217900	96.60	7668	3.40
1991	407640	96.66	14081	3.34
2001	520321	95.43	25429	4.66
2011	912206	95.00	49247	5.10

Source: Census of different years and compilation

Fig. No: 2 bar diagram presents cartographically the Composition of Urban ST and others (Non-ST) given in bar column from 1961 to 2011 Census.

Fig.No.2: Urban composition of ST and Others (Non-ST) in Tripura from 1961 to 2011 Census

Table No.5 presents the total Urban and Rural population of ST of Tripura. The Rural population of ST Predominantly forms about 96 percent and is considered as the major junk of population composition whereas Urban only forms only micro meager population.

Year	Total Population of the State	Total Urban Population of the State	Total Rural	Total ST population of the State	Total Urban ST	Total Rural ST
1961	1142005	102997	1039008	360074	3698	356376
1971	1556342	162360	1393982	450544	5485	445059
1981	2053058	225568	1827490	583920	7668	576252
1991	2757205	421721	2335484	853345	14081	839264
2001	3199203	545750	2258347	993426	25429	967997
2011	3673917	961453	2712464	1166813	49247	1117566

Source: Census of different years and compilation

Figure no.3 bar diagram presents rural and urban composition and its growth over time.

Table No.6 presents the decadal growth rate change of the urban population of ST and others.

Year	Rate of increase of other Urban Population	(%) Growth rate	Rate of increase of Urban population of ST	(%) Growth rate
1961-1971	+57576	57.98	+1787	48.32
1971-1981	+61025	38.90	+2183	39.79
1981-1991	+189,740	87.07	+6413	83.63
1991-2001	+112681	27.64	+11348	80.59
2001-2011	+391885	75.31	+23818	93.66

Source: Census of different years and compilation

The below Fig No.4 presents the line chart diagram where the ST urban population is showing a relatively flat trend line without much change of urban population over the decadal census periods.

(c). ST urban composition in the District level according to census 2011: The below Table No.7 and Figure No.5 presents the distribution of ST in both Rural and Urban in the eight districts of Tripura. West Tripura forms the significant proportion of ST in urban areas whereas Sepahijala district forms the lowest population figures living in urban areas.

District	Rural	Urban	Total	% to total Population
West Tripura District	149847	26749	176596	19.23
Sepahijala District	118385	1016	119401	24.69
Khowai District	138104	1433	139537	42.60
South Tripura District	151329	1362	152691	35.45
Gomati District	184007	4547	188554	42.70
North Tripura District	109696	7410	117106	28.05
Unakoti District	60561	1759	62320	22.54
Dhalai District	205637	4971	210608	55.68
TRIPURA	1117566	49247	1166813	31.76

Source: Census of India, 2011

(d). Urban composition of ST in the predominant Cities and towns of Tripura: According to the data from the Census of 2011, there are 8 districts, 23 sub-divisions, and 19 municipal towns in the state of Tripura. There is only one city in this state with a Municipal Corporation - Agartala and thirteen towns with Municipal Council as per the latest data.

Table No.8: ST Urban composition in the important Cities and towns of Tripura,2011 Census

SI	CITY/TOWN	ST	% to total Urban	TOTAL URBAN
1	Agartala city -municipal corporation	21359	5.37	397622
2	Dharmanagar city municipal council	235	0.57	40595
3	Udaipur mcouncil	172	0.52	32758
4	Kailashahar m council	415	1.85	22405
5	Bishal garh	23	0.10	21085
6	belonia	93	0.47	19921
7	Khowai m council	635	3.43	18526
8	Ambassa	922	5.66	16285
9	Teliamura	132	0.63	21032
10	Kumarghat	371	2.84	13054
11	Sabroom	230	3.22	7142
12	Manu	2639	30.99	8515
13	Kamalpur	188	1.73	10872
14	Melaghar	8414	67.45	12474
15	Mohanpur	52	0.37	14105
16	Sonamura	63	0.56	11285
17	Santir Bazar	366	3.07	11921
18	Jirania	2346	16.44	14269
19	Ranirbazar	19	0.14	13104
20	Panisagar	767	5.20	14758
21	Amarpur	186	1.72	10838
22	Kanchanpur	2575	16.78	15341

Sources: Census of India and Urban Department of Tripura

The capital City Agartala has a significant ST urban population in comparison with other cities and towns of Tripura. Some towns like Manu, Melaghar, and Khowai consists of comparatively ST population while many towns have negligible ST population not crossing over 1000 size of the population.

8. FEATURES OF THE SIXTH SCHEDULED AREA TTAADC AND ITS NATURE OF WORKING:

The TTAADC was set up under the sixth schedule on 1st April 1985 mainly for the protection of Tribal areas from the encroachment of Non-Tribal. It consists of more than 95 % of the ST population. Out of 10471 sq. km of the total state area, the area of the Sixth schedule area is 7132.56 sq. km which is about two-thirds of the total State area. There are about 527 village committees and not a single town has evolved from the function of TTAADC. The administrative functions have largely been dominated by rural developments of the Tribal. The role in developing the rural sector is even restricted because of the paucity of funds. The main feature of TTAADC is based on Village Committee and not on Town Council. It is to be noted out that even the Headquarter Khumulwng has not taken the shape of Town till yet, and which primarily consists of official buildings untouched by the urban culture and business hub. It is to be noted out that although TTAADC has about 7132.56 sq. km, the area under reserved forest holds about 6241.3 sq. km and is not under people's disposal.

It astonishes that only 891.26 sq. km is under settlements and of agricultural uses. The studies of schemes of TTAADC are primarily being devoted to tribal protections, rural development, and its protection under reserved forest areas. The town initiatives and building urban centers has not come in the implementation and working administrative process of TTAADC. In the recent period, there are some indications of incorporating town model developments. Map No.1 represents the urban exclusion spots of the TTAADC area.

9. GENERAL OBSERVATIONS OF SCHEDULED TRIBES AND ITS SHIFTING TRENDS FROM RURAL TO URBAN:

The majority of the Scheduled tribes of the world are predominantly rural-based with their specific relations with the hill and forest environment. It is also synonymous with the Tribals of Tripura whose populations are predominantly rural. It is being observed that some sections of the tribal from Sixth Scheduled areas have initiated shifting from rural settlement to urban area. The majority of the Tribal who are serving under government employees and well-to-do families have known to be purchasing some piece of land for settlement in the urban areas especially in the Capital city Agartala and some other important urban centers of Tripura. Many of the Scheduled Tribes students who are pursuing education in Schools and Colleges in the Towns and cities of Tripura are largely staying in the rent houses accommodation. It is increasingly seen that urban centers are attracting force for the educated tribal and the students for experiencing urban livelihood, and accessing secure life, medical facilities and pursuing education in modern institutions which are available only in the urban centers.

10. NEED FOR PROSPECT FOR URBAN CENTERS IN SIXTH SCHEDULED TRIBAL AREAS:

The main theme for regional development is building urban centers in some pocket areas. The total population engulfing in the rural traditional economy will not able to align themselves along with the modern economy. To follow as par the modern economy, the tribal need to go through urban phases as the urban centers are being treated as forces for economic development and raising educated citizens of the country. Most of the predominant ST states are showing the increasing trend of urbanization, while the Tribal of Tripura is reflecting staggering snail growth; although there are aspirations of many tribal who are attracted by urban centers. How far the major tribal people depend on the rural and forest economy? How far they can go on selling agricultural subsistence and forest products along the highways road? There needs to be thrust for changing livelihood patterns and introducing diverse economic activities to absorb the vast real unemployment rate of the Tribal. The below Picture plate No.1 reflects the predominant rural activities of the majority Tribal of Tripura.

Picture Plate No.1: Major Livelihood of the People of Tripura

Photo Courtesy: Internet sources

11. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

The study portrays and incurred some of the findings. They are as follows:-

(i). In North-East India, many STs are gradually forming part of the urban composition. In Tripura, urban centers have not sprung up from within tribal areas and so certain sections of ST have to shift from tribal rural areas to urban. It is to be stated that only certain specific well to do and Urban conscious social groups have migrated to urban centers. The cost of land in the urban areas of Tripura is unexpectedly high which

many of the tribal could not afford. That is the chief reason for very low urban composition than their counterparts scheduled tribes of North-east India.

(ii). The nature and working of the Sixth Scheduled administrative role are based on the protection of the tribes along with their rural habitat economy. There is not a single policy where the administrative function has come up with the concepts of Town building and Urban centers in the Sixth Schedule areas. The nature of the working of the Sixth schedule is village council and not based on Town Council. Under these circumstances, no towns and cities can sprout on their own, unless the government takes a primary initiative role in building a town by providing such urban life scopes.

(iii). The Urbanization process of Scheduled Tribes of Tripura shows the least Urbanized rate when compared with other Predominant ST States of North-East India. The decadal rate from 1961 to 2011 presents a snail stagnant growth rate with only a considerable spike from 2001 to 2011.

(iv). The Urban population of Schedule Tribes of Tripura is also reflecting the least composition. The Scheduled Tribes only form 5.10 % part of the urban composition of the State, while the lion share 95 % composition is still dominated by rural livelihood.

(v). There is not a single Town that can be identified in the Sixth-Scheduled areas. Even the headquarter Khumulwng lay only with official building premises but not have evolved into the full potential of Urban center.

(vi). The chief role functions of TTAADC administration are based on the land protection of Scheduled tribes and protection of forest areas. All the schemes of Sixth Scheduled are based on the building Village Model and not Town Model. It is to mention that the Sixth Scheduled areas are only being classified under village council and Reserved Forest areas.

(vii). The increasing trend of migration of Scheduled tribes is seen in the Capital Agartala and Khowai, Manu towns. Many of the Government employees are seen shifting from Rural to Urban for accessing urban amenities and meeting scopes for higher education. The settlements of ST in urban areas are urban dwellers and they are not involved in business economic activities. Some of the sections of Scheduled tribes are engaged with rickshaw pulling and petty vegetable vendors.

(viii). It is being observed and analyzed that 'power of purchasing classified ST group' has only been shifted to Urban areas, which has only boosted the town business activities dominated by Non-Tribal. This is a detrimental transfer of elite groups who could help the fellow ST rural people by purchasing by their subsistence agricultural products and also by engaging them for labour for domestic household activities and other purposes.

(viii). Among the 19 tribes, the Tripuri community (surname Debbarma) and Chakma community are displaying a comparative signification proportion of urban composition among their counterpart tribes. The tribes of tea tribes and Reang tribes are showing the lowest urban composition than their counterpart tribes.

(ix). The educated and business-minded Scheduled tribes of the modern-day have started knowing the importance of urban and towns and what it can do in employing the people in the realm of diverse economic activities. Many of the markets in scheduled Tribe areas are depicting the seller's groups of various items

where once the large tribal people are only seen to be buyers only with the predominance of selling of subsistence forest and agricultural products. The time has come for the change of Sixth Schedule areas administrative function to give prior attention to town building and urbanizing the ST population to some extent.

12. STRATEGIES AND SUGGESTIVE MEASURES:

In various parts of other North-East Indian States, the government takes a pioneering role in making the people urbanized through their system policies and effort. In Nagaland, the village concept is not much used. They used the name of the settlements in terms of 4th Mile and 6th mile etc as many of the settlements are along the roads. As the region is highly rugged terrain, accessing these interior hamlet settlements becomes difficult. The government of Mizoram and Meghalaya encourages the people to settle along the roads so that all urban amenities like electricity and water supply can be given easily to the settlers along the roads.

In Tripura too, such efforts can be taken to encourage the rural settlements for settling along the roads with their financial provision and allotment of fixed land. It is to be noted out that although settlements are arranged along the roads, their agricultural fields and lands can be located a little interior away from the roads so that they can utilize their land for agriculture purposes and not solely depending on the town activities with their house premises. Most of these Hills and Forest are under Reserved Forest. Tripura has beyond measure of reserved forest. It is to be identified out that although TTAADC has about 7132.56 sq. km, the area under reserved forest holds about 6241.3 sq. km which can be considered as a mega portion of land protection. Certain 1000 acres of land can be released along the national highway for a town building and the well-being of the Scheduled tribes.

The National highway-8, Assam-Agartala road, and the lifeline of Tripura treaded their major portion in hilly forested Sixth Scheduled tribal areas. The scenic characteristics of this highway are the dominance of hilly reserved forest which makes the highways feel insecure, isolated, and untouched by human settlements which should be made use for a vibrant urban economic hub. Roads are the primary basis for any kind of human development and economic activities. These deserted human settlements with their hilly forest terrain roads can be miraculously converted into economic life links for the people in the Sixth schedule tribal areas.

The government can create at least one center of an attractive zone in the Sixth Schedule areas by providing all urban amenities like Official buildings, Medical centers, Army base camps, Educational hubs, Marketing Center and also providing a wide array of scopes for large diverse economic activities. The provision of business loans for initiating their urban economic activities can be given to business aspirants of ST unemployed youths. The one suggestion and aspiration of my hope is to build at least one urban center along the national highway in the hill ranges of Baramura or Atharamura or Longthrai thereby selecting the most suitable spots for establishing an urban center. This compact settlement along the National highways with the policy of the government can lead to an evolving urban hub, attracting people for economic activities, secure livelihood, and attractive tourist spots with the signature of the only Hill Town station of Tripura. However, it is to be directed that settlements and business activities should be rightly reserved for the Scheduled Tribes of Tripura. Most of the government ST employees may be given free land allotment to such targeted urban spots to create purchasing power social groups and other

unemployed youths and citizens to establish their business. The picture plate below explains how the insecure hilly forest guarded with security forces along the National highway can be converted into a soothing hilly town station of the State. Picture Plate No.2 portrays a transforming Hilltown station along the national highway.

Picture Plate no 2: Design for urban development along the hilly forest terrain NH-8, Assam-Agartala road.

Photo courtesy: internet sources

There are about 22 Rural Developments Blocks located in the Sixth schedule areas. These 22 RD Blocks centers can be upgraded with much departmental administration function along with the provision scopes for a Town building spot. The government needs to strengthen such market centers to grow into towns by providing and aiding infrastructural and financial loans to the business aspirant community of the Scheduled Tribes. However, there should be cautions that many spots should not be chosen at once for developing urban centers, as the urban requires compact settlements and a large sizeable population for economic activities to operate between sellers and strong purchasing groups. The selecting of many spots for urban centers will lead to failure in raising even one Town of reputed potentials for business hubs and economic activities. The initiatives of setting many urban spots will result in market centers only and not towns. In the first phase, at least one or two urban model spots should be built up; sprouting mainly from the Scheduled tribe community and areas. In the later period, the distribution of at least one urban center in the district level comprising the Sixth Scheduled areas can be gradually approached as the selected spots for Town buildings.

13. Concluding Remarks: The study on the urbanization and urban composition of the Scheduled tribes of Tripura presents a wide array of information on the urban status of the tribals of Tripura. Through this study, the performance of urbanization and composition of the Tribal could be measured at the comparison level of North-East region, State, districts, and in various towns and cities of Tripura. The transition phases and shifting urban culture in the modern phase are being observed and identified out. The reasons for the low growth trend of urbanization in different census periods are being identified and traced out. The need for changing the developmental perspective of the Sixth Scheduled administrative function and its strategies and suggestive measures for a town building and urbanizing the tribes are laid out. However, the study

lacks certain information which can be derived from the Case study and extensive field survey on ST urban dwellers in various towns and cities of Tripura. The in-depth research may be carried out to get a better and clear picture of the Urbanization of the Tribes of Tripura.

14. REFERENCE AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Das Gupta, Malabika. 2014 '*Urbanisation and the Tribals of Tripura*', Book, Mittal Publications, Delhi
2. Khakha, Aashish. 2019 '*Tribes and Urbanisation in North East India-Issues and Challenges-Economic and Political weekly*' of Development Studies, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai.
3. Khawas, Vimal. 2003. '*Trend in Urbanization and Urban growth in the Eastern Indian Himalayas-The Case of Manipur, Sikkim and Tripura*'. www.mtnforum.org
4. Khawas, Vimal (2005) '*Urbanisation in the North-East: Patterns, trends, and policy prongs*' First Published June 1, 2005 Research Article Volume: 35 issue: 2, page(s): 47-69
5. Panchal, Bhavik, ed. 2020 '*Development Of Nodal Centre As Strategy For Balanced Regional Development*' International Journal of scientific & technology research volume 9, issue 04.
6. North-East Livelihood-Draft Final Report. May 2011 '*Social Assessment and Tribal Developmental Framework-*, Ministry of Development of North-Eastern Region.
7. Brahmhatt , Bijal (February 6, 2019) '*Urbanising around tribal land*' Diversity Inclusion, India Developmental Review Articles,
8. Census of India. 2011, *NER data basic Statistics bank*
9. District Hand Census Book of Tripura. 2011
10. Tripura at a Glance, 2019 Statistic Department, Govt. of Tripura
11. Conceptual Storm water Management Plan Report - Urban Development Department Government of Tripura
12. Annual Report-2016-17-Ministry of Tribal Affairs, Govt. of India
13. Websites of TTAADC, Sixth Scheduled Area